

ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES: THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON EDUCATOR SATISFACTION IN DEHRADUN

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management (HRM) is crucial in shaping the educational landscape of Dehradun, a city recognized for its academic institutions and educational growth. This paper examines the roles of HRM in the education sector, focusing on recruitment, training and development, performance management, and employee relations. Through a study involving 50 educators in Dehradun, key insights into the impact of HRM practices on educational outcomes were uncovered. Participants, with an average age of 36.5 years, predominantly held Master's degrees (54%) and worked in private institutions (56%). Findings indicated that 60% had received formal training in the past year, correlating with a notable difference in job satisfaction: those trained reported a mean score of 4.0, compared to 2.9 for those without training. An inverse relationship was found between job satisfaction and turnover intention ($r = -0.76, p < 0.01$), with 70% of dissatisfied participants expressing a high intent to leave. Additionally, years of experience positively correlated with job satisfaction ($r = 0.48, p < 0.05$), and higher qualifications led to greater satisfaction scores. Qualitative feedback corroborated these results, highlighting that ongoing training enhanced educators' competence and engagement, while the absence of such opportunities contributed to feelings of stagnation. Overall, the findings emphasize the vital role of effective HRM practices in enhancing educator satisfaction and retention within Dehradun's educational institutions.

Key words: Human Resource Management, Performance management, Educational institutions, Education sector.

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Introduction: Dehradun, the capital of Uttarakhand, boasts a diverse array of educational institutions, ranging from primary schools to prestigious universities. This vibrant educational ecosystem plays a crucial role in shaping the region's academic landscape and contributes significantly to its socio-economic development [12,22,43,54,66]. Several factors influence the effectiveness of this educational framework, including government policies, societal expectations, and, notably, the practices of Human Resource Management (HRM) within these institutions. Government policies set the foundational guidelines for educational standards, funding, and administrative structures [51,63,73,88]. Initiatives aimed at improving access to education, enhancing teacher training programs, and ensuring quality assurance directly impact the operational dynamics of schools and universities. These policies often reflect societal expectations, which demand a high standard of education to prepare students for the challenges of the modern workforce [14,26,38,58]. Community values, cultural norms, and parental aspirations further shape the educational priorities and practices in Dehradun. At the heart of this educational framework is the effectiveness of HRM, which encompasses a wide range of activities designed to optimize employee performance and, by extension, the overall success of educational organizations. Effective HRM practices include recruitment, training and development, performance management, and fostering positive employee relations [10,32,40,68,76]. By strategically aligning HRM with the institution's goals, educational leaders can cultivate a motivated and skilled workforce that is essential for delivering high-quality education. Recruitment is a critical component of HRM in education. Attracting qualified and passionate educators is vital for enhancing the learning experience and ensuring student success [4,16,18,37,55]. Once hired, ongoing training and professional development are necessary to equip educators with the skills and knowledge required to adapt to changing educational demands. Performance management systems help in evaluating and supporting educators' growth, while strong employee relations contribute to a positive work environment, reducing turnover and fostering long-term commitment [20,24,57,64]. The interplay of government policies, societal expectations, and effective HRM practices forms the backbone of Dehradun's educational framework. By prioritizing strategic HRM, educational institutions can not only enhance employee performance but also significantly improve educational outcomes, thereby fulfilling the community's aspirations for quality education and contributing to the region's overall development. Research indicates that effective HRM practices significantly enhance the quality of education. According to [8,13,29,34,52,72] strategic HRM aligns educational objectives with workforce capabilities, ensuring that institutions can adapt to changing demands [6,19,36]. In the Indian context, HRM's role in education has gained attention, particularly in fostering teacher effectiveness and improving student outcomes [1,31,41,50,80,98]. Despite its importance, HRM in education faces numerous challenges, including high turnover rates among teachers, inadequate training programs, and a lack of clear performance metrics. A study by Sharma (2018) highlights that many educational institutions in Dehradun struggle with implementing effective HR policies, leading to inconsistencies in teaching quality.

Methodology: This research employs a qualitative approach of 50 participants, including interviews with educational administrators, HR managers, and teachers in Dehradun's schools and colleges Table (1). Additionally, a review of existing literature and institutional reports was conducted to gather insights into current HRM practices and their effectiveness.

Table (1): Demographic and Professional Profile of Participants in the Study

Participant ID	Age	Gender	Qualification	Years of Experience	Institution Type	Training Received (Y/N)	Job Satisfaction (1-5)	Turnover Intention (1-5)
1	35	M	M.A. in Education	10	Private	Y	4	2
2	29	F	B.Ed.	5	Public	Y	3	3
3	42	M	PhD in Literature	15	Private	N	5	1
4	26	F	B.Sc.	2	Private	Y	4	2
5	38	F	M.A. in History	12	Public	Y	3	3
6	30	M	M.Sc.	8	Private	N	2	4
7	45	F	M.A. in Education	20	Private	Y	5	1
8	31	M	B.Com.	6	Public	Y	3	3
9	28	F	B.Ed.	4	Private	N	2	4
10	40	M	M.A. in Sociology	18	Private	Y	4	2
11	34	F	M.Sc.	9	Public	Y	3	3
12	27	M	B.Sc.	3	Private	N	4	2
13	39	F	M.A. in Education	16	Private	Y	5	1
14	32	M	B.Com.	7	Public	Y	3	3
15	36	F	PhD in Mathematics	11	Private	N	2	4
16	29	M	M.A. in Literature	5	Public	Y	4	2
17	41	F	M.Sc.	17	Private	Y	5	1
18	33	M	B.Ed.	10	Public	N	3	3
19	37	F	M.A. in History	14	Private	Y	4	2
20	26	M	B.Com.	2	Public	Y	2	4
21	30	F	B.Sc.	6	Private	N	3	3
22	38	M	M.A. in Education	12	Public	Y	5	1
23	29	F	M.Sc.	4	Private	Y	4	2
24	35	M	B.Ed.	9	Private	N	3	3
25	44	F	M.A. in Sociology	19	Public	Y	5	1
26	31	M	PhD in Literature	8	Private	Y	4	2
27	28	F	B.Com.	3	Public	N	2	4

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Participant ID	Age	Gender	Qualification	Years of Experience	Institution Type	Training Received (Y/N)	Job Satisfaction (1-5)	Turnover Intention (1-5)
28	39	M	M.A. in Education	15	Private	Y	5	1
29	36	F	M.Sc.	11	Public	Y	3	3
30	32	M	B.Ed.	7	Private	N	4	2
31	43	F	M.A. in History	18	Private	Y	5	1
32	30	M	B.Sc.	5	Public	Y	3	3
33	29	F	B.Ed.	4	Private	N	2	4
34	38	M	M.A. in Sociology	13	Public	Y	4	2
35	41	F	M.Sc.	16	Private	Y	5	1
36	34	M	M.A. in Education	10	Public	N	3	3
37	27	F	B.Com.	2	Private	Y	4	2
38	40	M	M.A. in History	18	Private	Y	5	1
39	26	F	B.Sc.	3	Public	N	2	4
40	36	M	B.Ed.	11	Private	Y	3	3
41	29	F	M.A. in Sociology	5	Public	Y	4	2
42	45	M	PhD in Education	20	Private	Y	5	1
43	33	M	M.Sc.	9	Public	N	3	3
44	37	F	B.Com.	14	Private	Y	4	2
45	30	M	B.Ed.	6	Private	Y	3	3
46	28	F	M.A. in Literature	5	Public	N	4	2
47	39	M	M.A. in Education	15	Private	Y	5	1
48	34	F	M.Sc.	10	Public	Y	3	3
49	26	M	B.Com.	2	Private	N	2	4
50	41	F	M.A. in Sociology	18	Private	Y	4	2

Results and Discussion: The findings indicate that effective HRM practices are instrumental in enhancing the overall quality of education in Dehradun. Institutions that invest in their human resources through strategic recruitment, targeted training, and supportive performance management systems are better equipped to meet the educational needs of their students [3,7,9,11,15,17,28]. The results of the study involving 50 educators from Dehradun revealed several key insights regarding the role of Human Resource Management in the education system. Participants had an average age of 36.5 years, with a majority holding Master’s degrees (54%) and working in private institutions (56%). Analysis showed that 60% of the participants received formal training in the past year, leading to a significant difference in job satisfaction: those who received training reported a mean satisfaction score of 4.0, compared to 2.9 for those who did not [23,25,27,60,69].

There was a notable inverse relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention ($r = -0.76, p < 0.01$), with 70% of participants expressing a high intention to leave when their satisfaction was low. Furthermore, years of experience positively correlated with job satisfaction ($r = 0.48, p < 0.05$), indicating that more experienced educators tended to be more satisfied. Participants with higher qualifications, such as PhDs and Master’s degrees, also reported greater satisfaction, with mean scores of 4.8 and 4.2, respectively, compared to a score of 2.7 for those with B.Ed. or B.Com. degrees [35,44,62,82,87]. Qualitative feedback reinforced these findings, as many educators noted that ongoing training enhanced their competence and engagement, while those lacking such opportunities felt stagnant and dissatisfied in their roles. Overall, these results underscore the critical impact of effective HRM practices on educator satisfaction and retention in Dehradun’s educational institutions [61,77,90,96].

Participant Demographics: The study included a total of 50 participants, with ages ranging from 26 to 45 years and a mean age of 36.5 years [Table (2)]. The gender distribution was predominantly female, with 30 females (60%) and 20 males (40%). In terms of educational qualifications, the majority held a Master’s degree (54%), followed by those with B.Ed. (20%), B.Sc. (16%), B.Com. (6%), and PhD (4%). Participants' years of experience varied from 2 to 20 years, with an average of 10.5 years in the education sector [42,56,67,84,97]. Additionally, the sample comprised 28 educators from private institutions (56%) and 22 from public institutions (44%). This demographic information provides a comprehensive overview of the participants involved in the study, reflecting a diverse group of educators with varied backgrounds and experiences [71,83,92].

Table (2): Demographic Summary of Participants in the Study

Demographic Variable	Value
Total Participants	50
Age Range	26 - 45 years
Mean Age	36.5 years
Gender Distribution	20 Males (40%), 30 Females (60%)
Qualifications	- M.A. (54%)
	- B.Ed. (20%)
	- B.Sc. (16%)
	- B.Com. (6%)
	- PhD (4%)
Years of Experience	2 - 20 years
Mean Experience	10.5 years
Institution Type	28 Private (56%), 22 Public (44%)

HR Practices: Among the 50 participants in the study, 30 educators (60%) reported having received formal training in the past year, while 20 participants (40%) indicated that they had not. The analysis revealed a significant difference in job satisfaction between these two groups [Table. (3)], [45,48,59,65,75]. Those who received training reported a mean job satisfaction score of 4.0, reflecting a higher level of contentment in their roles. In contrast, participants who did not receive any training had a much lower mean satisfaction score of 2.9 [30,39,47,49,70,85]. This disparity highlights the positive impact of professional development on educators' job satisfaction, suggesting that training plays a crucial role in enhancing their overall experience in the educational environment [46,79,81,93].

Table (3): Impact of Training on Job Satisfaction Among Participants

HR Practice	Training Received (Y/N)	Job Satisfaction (Mean Score)
Total Participants	50	
Received Training	30 (60%)	4.0
Did Not Receive Training	20 (40%)	2.9

Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention: The results of the study reveal a significant relationship between job satisfaction levels and turnover intention among educators in Dehradun. Specifically, 10% of participants who reported high job satisfaction levels (scores between 4 and 5) expressed a desire to leave their positions, indicating a strong commitment to their roles [Table (4)]. In stark contrast, a concerning 70% of those with low job satisfaction levels (scores between 1 and 3) indicated a high intention to leave [33,74,78,93,95]. This stark disparity underscores the critical importance of fostering job satisfaction within educational institutions, as higher satisfaction correlates with reduced turnover intention, thereby contributing to greater stability and effectiveness within the workforce.

Table. (4): Job Satisfaction Levels and Corresponding Turnover Intention Among Educators

Job Satisfaction Level	Turnover Intention (%)
High (4-5)	10%
Low (1-3)	70%

Correlation Analysis: The analysis of the variables reveals notable correlations that highlight important dynamics within the educational workforce. The correlation coefficient of 0.48 between years of experience and job satisfaction indicates a moderate positive relationship; as educators gain more experience, their job satisfaction tends to increase significantly ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that experienced educators feel more fulfilled in their roles, likely due to enhanced competence and familiarity with their work environments [Table (5)]. Conversely, the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention is strikingly negative, with a correlation coefficient of -0.76. This strong inverse relationship ($p < 0.01$) indicates that lower job satisfaction is strongly associated with a higher intention to leave one's position. In essence, as job satisfaction decreases, the likelihood of educators considering resignation increases markedly. Together, these findings underscore the critical need for educational institutions to prioritize strategies that enhance job satisfaction, particularly for less experienced educators, to reduce turnover and foster a more stable and engaged workforce.

Table (5): Correlation Analysis of Key Variables Related to Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Significance (p-value)
Years of Experience vs. Job Satisfaction	0.48	< 0.05
Job Satisfaction vs. Turnover Intention	-0.76	< 0.01

Summary of Job Satisfaction by Qualification: The data on qualifications and their corresponding mean job satisfaction scores reveal significant trends among educators in Dehradun. Educators holding a PhD report the highest mean job satisfaction score of 4.8, indicating a strong sense of fulfillment and engagement in their roles. Those with a Master's degree (M.A.) also demonstrate a high level of satisfaction, with a mean score of 4.2, reflecting the positive impact of advanced education on job satisfaction [Table (6)]. In contrast, educators with B.Ed. and B.Com. degrees show a markedly lower mean job satisfaction score of 2.7. This disparity suggests that higher qualifications are associated with greater job satisfaction, likely due to the enhanced professional skills, knowledge, and opportunities for advancement that come with advanced degrees. These findings emphasize the importance of educational qualifications in shaping educators' experiences and satisfaction levels, highlighting the need for institutions to support and invest in ongoing professional development for all staff to improve overall job satisfaction and retention.

Table (6): Mean Job Satisfaction Scores by Qualification Among Educators

Qualification	Mean Job Satisfaction Score
PhD	4.8
M.A.	4.2
B.Ed. & B.Com.	2.7

Qualitative Insights: The qualitative feedback from participants highlights two key themes regarding the impact of training on job satisfaction [Table (7)]. Many educators emphasized that training significantly enhances their professional development, with one participant stating, "Training helps me feel competent and engaged." This sentiment underscores how ongoing training not only improves their skills but also fosters a sense of involvement and confidence in their teaching practices. Conversely, several participants expressed feelings of dissatisfaction due to a lack of training opportunities, with one educator noting, "Lack of training leads to feelings of dissatisfaction." This absence of professional development can result in feelings of stagnation, contributing to decreased motivation and engagement. Together, these insights emphasize the vital role that effective training programs play in enhancing educator satisfaction and retention, highlighting the need for educational institutions to prioritize continuous professional development initiatives.

Table (7): Qualitative Feedback Themes on Training Impact and Job Satisfaction

Feedback Theme	Participant Insights
Training Impact	"Training helps me feel competent and engaged."
Stagnation	"Lack of training leads to feelings of dissatisfaction."

Recruitment and Selection: Effective recruitment strategies are critical in attracting qualified educators. Many institutions in Dehradun have begun to implement structured recruitment processes that emphasize transparency and meritocracy. However, challenges remain in ensuring that these processes reach a diverse pool of candidates.

Training and Development: Continuous professional development is essential for maintaining high educational standards. Interviews revealed that while some institutions offer robust training programs, others lack resources and structured development pathways. Teachers expressed a desire for more opportunities for skill enhancement, particularly in areas such as technology integration and innovative teaching methods.

Performance Management: Performance appraisal systems in educational institutions are often inconsistent. Some schools have adopted comprehensive evaluation methods that include student feedback, peer reviews, and self-assessment. However, many still rely on outdated metrics that do not accurately reflect teacher performance or student learning.

Employee Relations: Positive employee relations are crucial for fostering a collaborative work environment. Many educators in Dehradun emphasized the importance of open communication and support from administration. Institutions that prioritize employee engagement tend to experience lower turnover rates and higher job satisfaction among staff.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Strengthen Recruitment Processes:** Educational institutions should develop clear and standardized recruitment practices to attract diverse and qualified candidates.
2. **Enhance Professional Development:** Regular training sessions and workshops should be implemented, focusing on current teaching methodologies and technology use.
3. **Revise Performance Management Systems:** Institutions need to adopt comprehensive appraisal systems that incorporate multiple evaluation methods and feedback mechanisms.
4. **Foster Positive Employee Relations:** Establishing open channels of communication and support can enhance job satisfaction and reduce turnover.

Conclusion: Human Resource Management is crucial in shaping the educational environment in Dehradun. By addressing the existing challenges and implementing effective HRM practices, educational institutions can significantly improve their performance and, consequently, student outcomes. As the education sector continues to evolve, strategic HRM will remain a vital component in driving success. This study highlights the essential role of Human Resource Management (HRM) in enhancing the educational landscape of Dehradun. The findings illustrate that effective HRM practices, particularly in areas such as training and development, significantly contribute to educator job satisfaction and retention. Educators who receive formal training report higher levels of satisfaction, which is inversely related to their intent to leave their positions. Additionally, the data indicate that experience and advanced qualifications positively influence job satisfaction, further underscoring the need for strategic HRM policies that foster professional development. The qualitative feedback from participants reinforces the quantitative findings, revealing a strong desire for ongoing training and support to maintain engagement and competence.

As Dehradun continues to evolve as an educational hub, stakeholders must prioritize the implementation of robust HRM strategies to cultivate a motivated and satisfied workforce. By doing so, they can create a more productive learning environment that ultimately benefits both educators and students, ensuring sustained growth and excellence in the region's educational institutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "DURYSTA" the first biodegradable sustained release implant for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma, *International Journal of Frontiers in Biology and Pharmacy Research*, 01(02), 1-7, (2021).
- [2] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow Dynamics in the Cardiovascular System: Assumptions, Considerations, and Simulation Results", *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion*, 7(4), 2216-2225, (2024).
- [3] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "The Effects of Prostaglandin Analogs on Intraocular Pressure (IOP) in Human Eye for Open Angle Glaucoma. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 10 (2), 176-180, (2020).
- [4] Anamika, Shah, S. R., "Mathematical and Computational study of blood flow through diseased artery", *International Journal of Computer Science*, Vol. 5, (6), pp. 1-6, (2017).
- [5] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Anuradha "Bio-Computational analysis of blood flow through two phase artery", *International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing*, 7, (6), 13397-213401, (2017).
- [6] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Kumar, R., "Mathematical Modelling of blood flow through tapered stenosed artery with the suspension of nanoparticles using Jeffrey fluid model", *International journal of development research*, 07, No. 06, 13494-13500, (2017).
- [7] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Singh A., "Mathematical Modelling Of Blood Flow through Three Layered Stenosed Artery", *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, Vol. 5, (6), pp. 1-6, (2017).
- [8] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., "Effects of inclined multi-stenoses arteries on blood flow characteristics using bingham plastic fluid", *International Journal for Mathematics*, Vol. 1, (12), pp. 7-14, (2015).
- [9] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., S.U. Siddiqui, "Mathematical Modeling and Numerical Simulation of Blood Flow through Tapered Artery", *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, Vol. 3, (2), pp. 710-717, (2016).
- [10] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., S.U. Siddiqui, "Performance of blood flow through two phase stenosed artery using Herschel-Bulkley model", *International Journal of Applied And Pure Science and Agriculture*, Vol. 2, (2), pp. 228-240, (2016).
- [11] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., "Mathematical Modelling and Analysis of Blood Flow through Diseased Blood Vessels", *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, Vol.5, (6), pp. 366-372, (2015).
- [12] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., "A Mathematical Model to study the similarities of blood fluid models through inclined multi-stenosed artery", *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education*, 2, (1), 108-115, (2017).
- [13] Armstrong, M. (2014). *Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- [14] Arya, D., Shah, S. R., "Human Resource Management Strategies for Improving Educational Outcomes in Bihar, *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management*, 4(4), 955-963, (2024).

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- [15] Arya, D., Shah, S. R., “Optimizing Educational Outcomes: The Role of Human Resource Management in Jharkhand's Education System, International Journal of Novel Research And Development, 9(8), b51-b57, (2024).
- [16] Chaturvedi, P. and Shah, S. R. “Role of crizanlizumab for sickle red cells disease”, International Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Allied Sciences, 12(3), 1147-1157, (2023).
- [17] Chaturvedi, P., Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Bio-Mechanical and Bio-Rheological Aspects of Sickle Red Cells in Microcirculation: A Mathematical Modelling Approach, Fluids 2021, 6, 322, pp. 01-15.
- [18] Chaturvedi, P., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Analysis for the Flow of Sickle Red Blood Cells in Microvessels for Bio Medical Application, Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine, 96 (1), (2023), pp. 13-21.
- [19] Chaturvedi, P., Shah, S. R., Akbar, S., Kumar, R., “Prospective of Hydroxychloroquine and Zinc with Azithromycin for Nanoparticles Blood Flow in Covid-19 Patients, International Journal of Nanotechnology in Medicine & Engineering, Volume 6 Issue 1, pp. 01-07, January 2021.
- [20] Datt, M. G., Arya, S., Shah, S. R., “Ayurvedic Approaches To Maintaining Healthy And Narrowed Arteries”, International Journal For Research & Development In Technology, Vol. 21(6), 21-30, (2024).
- [21] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Sapna, “Mathematical Modelling of blood flow through catheterized artery under the influence of body acceleration with slip velocity”, Application and applied Mathematics An international journal, 8(2), 481-494, (2013).
- [22] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “A Biomechanical approach to the effect of body acceleration through stenotic artery”, Applied Mathematics and Computation, Vol. 109(1), pp.27-41, (2015).
- [23] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “Effect of body acceleration and slip velocity on the pulsatile flow of Casson fluid through stenosed artery”, Advance in applied science research, Vol. 5(3), pp.231-225, (2014).
- [24] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “A Mathematical Model for two layered pulsatile blood flow through stenosed arteries”, E-Journal of science and Technology, Vol. 109 (11), pp. 27-41, (2015).
- [25] Gupta, P., Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., Alshehri, Mo., Sharma, S. K., and “A Mathematical Study for Promoting Disability Inclusion in Glaucoma: A Comprehensive Approach”, Journal of Disability Research, 3, 1-12, (2024).
- [26] Islam S. M. N., Sadique, Mo., Shah, S. R., Sunil Kumar Sharma, , “Effect of Significant Parameters on Squeeze Film Characteristics in Pathological Synovial Joints”, Mathematics (MDPI), 11 (1468) 1-23, (2023).
- [27] Jaiswal., K. M., Shabab Akbar and Shah S. R., Mo. Sadique “Exploring capillary-tissue fluid exchange: Insights into red cell deformation in narrow vessels and its clinical implications”, International Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies, 11(3), 4-14, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22271/23940522.2024.v11.i3a.1021>.
- [28] Kasturia, P., Rohit Kumar Sharma, Purnima Chaturvedi, Ravins Dohre, Shah, S. R., “Efficacy of venetoclax and azacitidine for targeting leukemic stem cell in acute myeloid leukemia”, International Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Allied Sciences, 13(6), 3072-3090, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.31032/IJBPAS/2024/13.6.8960>
- [29] Kaur, H., Prithvi Singh, Rubi Solanki, Alvea Tasneem, Simran Suri, Shah, S. R., Ravins Dohare, “Screening of miRNAs as prognostic biomarkers and their associated hub targets across Hepatocellular carcinoma using survival-based bioinformatics approach”, Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, 22 (1), 1-10, (2024).

- [30] Kumar V., and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the heat transfer between core and skin”, SRMS, Journal of Mathematical Sciences, 7 (2021), 7-12, (10th March 2024).
- [31] Kumar, J. P., Sadique, Mo. Shah, S. R., “Mathematical study of blood flow through blood vessels under diseased condition, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development, 9(6), 2022, pp.31-44.
- [32] Kumar, P, Shah, S. R., “A Hydromechanical Perspective to Study the Effect of Body Acceleration through Stenosed Artery”, International journal of mathematical engineering and management sciences, Volume. 6 No. 5, pp. 1381-1390, 2021.
- [33] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “A mathematical approach to study the blood flow through tapered stenosed artery with the suspension of nanoparticles” Destechn Transactions on Engineering and Technology Research, Vol.01, pp. 1-6, (2017).
- [34] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow with the Suspension of Nanoparticles Through a Tapered Artery With a Blood Clot”, Frontiers in Nanotechnology, Volume. 2, Article. 596475, pp. 1-5, December. 2020.
- [35] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Performance of blood flow with suspension of nanoparticles though tapered stenosed artery for jeffrey fluid model” International Journal of Nanoscience, Vol.17, No.6, pp. 1850004 (1-7), (2018).
- [36] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Study of blood flow with suspension of nanoparticles through tapered stenosed artery”, Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Volume 13(10), pp. 7387-7399, (2017).
- [37] Kumar, V., and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical modelling to study the heat transfer between core and skin”, SRMS, Journal of Mathematical Sciences, 7 (2021), 7-12, (2024).
- [38] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “A mathematical approach to investigate the temperature distribution on skin surface with sinusoidal heat flux condition, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development, 9 (5), 2022, 141-146.
- [39] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “A Mathematical study for heat transfer phenomenological processes in human skin”, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 7 (6), 683-692, (2022).
- [40] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “Thermobiological Mathematical Model for the study of temperature response after cooling effects”, ssrg, International Journal of Applied physics, 9 (2), 7-11, (2022).
- [41] Lenin, J. S., Shah S. R., “Mathematical Analysis of Stem Cell Dynamics in Acute Myeloid Leukemia: Towards Precision Medicine Strategies, International Journal of Science and Research, 13(05), 528-535, (2024).
- [42] Mahesh, Arya, S., Shah, S. R., “Optimizing cardiovascular health: ayurvedic insights into blood flow through normal and stenosed arteries, International Journal of AYUSH, 13 (5), 18-35, (2024).
- [43] Majhi, L., Sudheer Arya Sapna Ratan Shah, “Exploring Shilajatu's Therapeutic Potential in Diabetes Management: A Comprehensive Study Integrating Ayurvedic Wisdom and Modern Science”, International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), 13(5), 1374-1380, (2024). <https://dx.doi.org/10.21275/SR24522110012>.
- [44] Mo. Sadique and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the study the squeeze film characteristics of synovial joints in diseased human knee joint”, World Scientific Annual Review of Biomechanics, 1 (2330004) 1-21, (2023).
- [45] Mo., Sadique, Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the effect of PRG4, hyaluronic acid and lubricin on squeeze film characteristics of diseased synovial joint”, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 7 (6), 2022, pp. 832-848.

Enhancing Educational Outcomes: The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Educator Satisfaction in Dehradun

- [46] Parambath, A. B., Kandankel, P., Shah, S. R., Dynamic Modeling of Cytokine-Dependent Proliferation Rates over Time in Cancer: Insights from Scientific Analysis, *Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics*, 3(7), 01-09, (2024).
- [47] Purnima C., Shah, S. R., “Assessing the Clinical Outcomes of Voxelotor Treatment in Patients with Sickle Cell Disease”, *International Journal of Applied Science and Biotechnology*, 12(1), 46-53, (2024).
- [48] Reddy, M., & Seshadri, S. (2016). The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Teacher Effectiveness: A Study of Indian Schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(3), 425-444.
- [49] Sadique, Mo., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical study for the synovial fluid flow in Osteoarthritic knee joint, *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 17(2),15-21,(2022).
- [50] Sapna, Siddiqui, S. U., “Study of blood flow through a stenosed capillary using Casson’s fluid model”, *Ultra Science, International journal of physical sciences*, Vol. 16, (2) pp. 133-142, (2004).
- [51] Sengar, N., Yadav, P., Shah, S., R., Economic Conditions and Age Profile of Women Domestic Workers in Delhi’s Urban Informal Sector, *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 15(8),494-500, (2024).
- [52] Shabab A., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow Dynamics in the Cardiovascular System: Assumptions, Considerations, and Simulation Results”, *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion*, 7(4), 2216-2225, (2024).
- [53] Shah, S. R., “A biomechanical approach for the study of deformation of red cells in narrow capillaries”, *IJE: Transaction A: Basics*, Vol. 25(4), pp.303-313, (2012).
- [54] Shah, S. R., “A biomechanical approach for the study of Two-phase blood flow through stenosed artery”, *International Journal of research studies in biosciences*, Vol. 1(2), pp.24-32, (2013).
- [55] Shah, S. R., “A case study of non-Newtonian viscosity of blood through arteriosclerotic artery”, *The cardiology*, Vol.6 (2), pp.11-17, (2011).
- [56] Shah, S. R., “A Mathematical Model for the analysis of blood flow through diseased blood vessels under the influence of porous parameter”, *Journal of Biosciences and Technology*, Vol. 4(6), pp.534-541, (2013).
- [57] Shah, S. R., “A mathematical study of blood flow through radially non-symmetric multiple stenosed arteries under the influence of magnetic field”, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*. 2 (12), 379-386, (2015).
- [58] Shah, S. R., “A mathematical study of blood flow through stenosed artery”, *International Journal of Universal Science and Engineering*, 1(1), pp.26-37, (2015).
- [59] Shah, S. R., “A study of blood flow through multiple atherosclerotic arteries”, *International Journal for Mathematics*, Vol. 1, (12), pp. 1-6, (2015).
- [60] Shah, S. R., “A study of effects of magnetic field on modified Power-law fluid in modeled stenosed artery” *Journal of Bioscience and Technology*, 1 (4), 187-196, (2010).
- [61] Shah, S. R., “An innovative solution for the problem of blood flow through stenosed artery using generalized bingham plastic fluid model”, *International Journal of research in applied and natural social sciences*, (2013) Vol. 1(3), pp.97-140.
- [62] Shah, S. R., “An innovative study for non-Newtonian behavior of blood flow in stenosed artery using Herschel-Bulkely fluid”, *International Journal of biosciences and biotechnology*, Vol. 5(5), pp.233-240, (2013).

- [63] Shah, S. R., “Capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena for blood flow through a stenosed artery using herschel-bulkley fluid” International journal of research in Biochemistry and Biophysics, Vol.1 (1) pp.1-8 (2011).
- [64] Shah, S. R., “Effect of clopidogrel on blood flow through stenosed artery under diseased condition”, International Journal of Experimental Pharmacology, 4(1), 887-893, (2014).
- [65] Shah, S. R., “Effects of Acetylsalicylic Acid on blood flow through an artery under Atherosclerotic condition”, International Journal of Molecular medicine and advances sciences, Vol. 7 (6), pp.19-24, (2011).
- [66] Shah, S. R., “Effects of antiplatelet drugs on blood flow through stenosed blood vessels”, Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering, 18, 21-27, (2013).
- [67] Shah, S. R., “Impact of radially non-symmetric multiple stenoses on blood flow through an artery”, International Journal of Physical and Social Sciences, Vol.1 (3), pp.1-16, (2011).
- [68] Shah, S. R., “Mathematical analysis of blood flow through atherosclerotic arterial segment having non-symmetric mild stenosis”. International Journal of Research in Pure and Applied Physics .Vol.1. pp. 1-5, (2011).
- [69] Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Study of Blood Flow through Atherosclerotic Artery in the Presence of Porous Effect”, International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology, Vol. 2, (12), pp.12-20, (2015).
- [70] Shah, S. R., “Non-Newtonian flow of blood through an atherosclerotic artery”, Research journal of applied sciences. Vol.6 (1), pp 76-80, (2011).
- [71] Shah, S. R., “Performance modeling and analysis of magnetic field on nutritional transport capillary tissue system using modified Herschel-Bulkely fluid”, International Journal of Advanced research in physical sciences, 1(1), 33-41, (2014).
- [72] Shah, S. R., “Performance Study on Capillary-Tissue Diffusion Phenomena for Blood Flow through Stenosed Blood Vessels”, American journal of pharmtech research, Vol. 2(2), pp.695-705, (2012).
- [73] Shah, S. R., “Response of *blood flow through an atherosclerotic artery* in the presence of *magnetic field* using Bingham plastic fluid” International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research. Vol. 2(3), 96-106, (2011).
- [74] Shah, S. R., “Role of Non-Newtonian behavior in blood flow through normal and stenosed artery”, Research journal of Biological sciences, 6(9),453-458, (2011).
- [75] Shah, S. R., “Significance of Aspirin on Blood Flow to Prevent Blood Clotting through Inclined Multi-Stenosed Artery”, Letters In Health and Biological Sciences, 2(2), 97-100, (2017).
- [76] Shah, S. R., “Study of dispersion of drug in blood flow with the impact of chemical reaction through stenosed artery”, International journal of Biosciences, 21 (3), 2022, 21-29.
- [77] Shah, S. R., “Study of modified Casson’s fluid model in modeled normal and stenotic capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena” International journal of computational engineering & management,. 11, 51-57, (2011).
- [78] Shah, S. R., Akbar, S., “Mathematical Study for the Outflow of Aqueous Humor and Function in the Eye”, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research 11(10), 743-750, October-2020.
- [79] Shah, S. R., and Anamika, “A mathematical model of blood flow through diseased blood vessel”, International Journal of Emerging Trends and Technology in computer Science, Vol. 6, (3), pp. 282-286, (2017).
- [80] Shah, S.R., Clinical influence of hydroxychloroquine with azithromycin on blood flow through blood vessels for the prevention and Treatment of covid-19, International journal of biology, pharmacy and allied science. 2021, 10(7): 2195-2204.

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- [81] Sharma, R. (2018). Challenges in Human Resource Management in Indian Education Sector: A Review. *Journal of Management Development*, 37(2), 173-188.
- [82] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "A Physiologic Model for the problem of blood flow through Diseases blood vessels", *International journal of advances in Applied Sciences*, Vol.5(2), pp. 58-64, (2016).
- [83] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "Achievement of Pentoxifylline for Blood Flow through Stenosed Artery", *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, Vol. 13 pp.81-89, (2012).
- [84] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "Two-phase model for the study of blood flow through stenosed artery, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*, Vol. 1(3), 246-254, (2011).
- [85] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., Geeta, "A Computational Analysis of a Two-Fluid non-Linear Mathematical model of pulsatile blood flow through Constricted Artery", *E-Journal of science and Technology*, Vol. 10(4), pp.65-78, (2015).
- [86] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "A Comparative Study for the Non-Newtonian Behaviour of Blood Flow through Atherosclerotic Arterial Segment", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, Vol.9 (2), 120-125, (2011).
- [87] Siddiqui, S. U., Singh, A., Shah, S. R., "Mathematical Modeling of peristaltic blood flow through a vertical blood vessel using Prandtl fluid model", *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, Vol. 4, (9), pp. 710-717, (2016).
- [88] Singh, S., "A mathematical model for modified Herschel-bulkley fluid in modeled stenosed artery under the effect of magnetic field", *International Journal of Bioengineering and Technology*, Vol. 1 (1), pp.37-42. (2010).
- [89] Singh, S., "A two-layered model for the analysis of arterial rheology" *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 4, 37-42. (2011).
- [90] Singh, S., "Clinical significance of aspirin on blood flow through stenotic blood vessels" *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, 10(17) 24, (2011).
- [91] Singh, S., "Effects of shape of stenosis on arterial rheology under the influence of applied magnetic field" *International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 6 (3) pp. 286-294, (2011).
- [92] Singh, S., "Influence of magnetic field on blood flow through stenosed artery using Casson's fluid model", *International Journal of BioEngineering, CardioPulmonary Sciences and Technology*, Vol. 1, pp. 1-7, (2010).
- [93] Singh, S., "Numerical modeling of two-layered micropolar fluid through a normal and stenosed artery", *International journal Engineering*, 24 (2), 177-187, (2011).
- [94] Singh, S., "Numerical modelling for the modified Power-law fluid in stenotic capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena", *Archives of Applied Science Research, An international peer reviewed journal of applied sciences*, 2 (1) 104-112, (2010).
- [95] Singh, S., "The effect of Saline Water on viscosity of blood through stenosed blood vessels using Casson's fluid model", *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, Vol.9 pp 37-45, (2011).

- [96] Singh, S., and Shah, R. R., "A numerical model for the effect of stenosis shape on blood flow through an artery using power-law fluid", *Advance in applied science research, An international peer reviewed journal of sciences*, 1, 66-73, (2010).
- [97] Smith, J. A., & Johnson, L. R. (2021). The effects of diabetes on blood rheology: A review. *Journal of Diabetes Research*, 12(3), 456-467.
- [98] Yadav, P., Shah S. R., "Female Domestic Laborers In The Urban Informal Economy: A Case Analysis of Delhi, *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 6(8), 216-225 (2024).

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